

THE EFFECT OF INTERNAL MARKETING ON PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of internal marketing on physical education and sports teachers' job performance. Data were obtained from physical education and sports teachers (N=157) working in public institutions in Turkey. The data were collected with two scales measuring internal marketing and job performance. Descriptive analysis, validity and reliability analysis, correlation, and hierarchical regression analysis were applied to the obtained data. Validity and reliability analysis showed that both scales are highly valid and reliable. As a result of the hierarchical regression analysis, it was seen that internal marketing had a significant and positive effect on physical education and sports teachers' job performance. In order for education managers to achieve high performance in their organizations, they are suggested to apply internal marketing effectively.

Keywords: internal marketing, job performance, physical education, sports teacher

1. Introduction

The competitive environment, which has been increasingly intensified recently, forces education organizations to be successful, as in every field (Dee, 1998). It is known that success can only be achieved with high-quality service production. It is emphasized that the most important element in quality service production is human resources (Yildiz, 2008). In educational organizations with high labor intensity, teachers are the most important elements among human resources. In reaching quality service production, the teacher must be of superior quality. However, this is not enough, but teachers must be motivated by the organization in achieving organizational goals (Milanowski, 2000). Real organizational success is possible by attracting qualified teachers and motivating them. The motivated teacher by his organization will perform high, which will lead to organizational success (Müller, Alliata, and Benninghoff, 2009). At this point, the internal

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marketing concept, which is effective in creating employees with high job performance, becomes important for educational organizations.

Job performance is a concept that quantitatively and qualitatively indicates how much an individual doing a job reaches the purpose of that job (Schermerhorn et al., 2012). Internal marketing, on the other hand, is a marketing approach that attracts, retains, and motivates qualified employees to create effective external marketing as a competitive tool (Varey and Lewis, 1999). In order to understand internal marketing, it is necessary to know the concepts of internal customers and external customers first. The internal marketing approach divides the customer into two as internal and external customers. While the external customer refers to the person who purchases products from an organization, the internal customer means the employees producing in an organization (Bansal, Mendelson, and Sharma, 2001). The internal marketing approach suggests that external customer satisfaction is provided by internal customers, that is, employees, so that the internal customer must be satisfied first. In other words, it emphasizes that employees are the main factor that ensures the satisfaction of foreign customers (Berry, 1995). Rafiq and Ahmed (2000) divided internal marketing into three phases.

- The employee satisfaction phase; first of all, to get satisfied with external customers, it is necessary to have satisfied employees. This phase refers to treating employees as external customers.
- The customer-orientation phase; satisfaction affects the external client's more purchasing behavior. Therefore, employees should be sales-oriented and customer-oriented.
- The strategy implementation and change management phase; this is the improvement of internal communication by putting forward satisfaction strategies effectively.

Thus, internal friction will be reduced and employees will focus on external customers. As a result, when the internal marketing approach is effectively implemented by organizations, it offers a sustainable competitive advantage (Varey, 1995).

In the literature, there are various measurement tools for the measurement of internal marketing. The most used of these is the internal marketing scale of Meyer and Allen (1991). Using these measurement tools, for example, the relationship between internal marketing and other variables in the sports sector by Yildiz (2011a) was examined, and it was seen that internal marketing positively affected the job satisfaction and organizational commitment of the employees. More specifically, Yildiz and Kara (2017) developed a scale with a focus on academicians in higher educational institutions. Then, using this scale, various studies were carried out on teachers. Dokuzoglu and Eren (2020) examined the effect of internal marketing on organizational commitment of physical education and sports teachers, and Eren and Dokuzoglu (2020) investigated the effect of internal marketing on turnover intentions of physical education sports teachers. On the other hand, in the literature, there is no research examining the effect of internal marketing on job performance of physical education and sports teachers. Therefore, in

this study, it was aimed to examine the effect of internal marketing on physical education and sports teachers' job performance.

2. Method

2.1. Study Group

In this study, the data were obtained from physical education and sports teachers working in public schools in Turkey. First, an invitation message was sent to teachers containing information about working with electronic communication tools. Then, a questionnaire was sent to the teachers who agreed to participate in the study. The questionnaire forms returned after one week were determined to be 157.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

In this study, the IM-11 Scale developed by Yildiz and Kara (2017) to measure internal marketing was used as the data collection tool, and the job performance scale developed by Sigler and Pearson (2000) to measure job performance. The statements on the IM-11 scale were measured with a 5-point Likert grade (in the range of "1 = Disagree, 5 = Agree"). The statements on the job performance scale were measured with a 7-point Likert rating (in the range of "1 = Never, 7 = Always").

2.3. Data Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis was used to determine the construct validity of the scales and Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to determine its reliability. In the next step, correlation analysis was applied to determine the relationships between the variables. The effect of internal marketing on job performance has been tried to be determined by hierarchical regression.

3. Results

3.1. Sample Characteristics

Three-quarters of the participants are male, and three-quarters are married. The majority of the participants are between the ages of 36-45 (46.5%) and have an undergraduate degree (85.4%). Considering the working life variable, the majority of the participants (27.4%) work for 21-25 years in their institution (Table 1).

Table 1: Sample characteristics

Variables	Categories	f	%
Gender	Male	119	75.8
	Female	38	24.2
Marital status	Married	120	76.4
	Single	37	23.6
Age	Less than 25	2	4.3
	26-35	32	20.4

	36-45	73	46.5
	46-55	43	27.4
	More than 56	7	4.5
Degree	Undergraduate	134	85.4
	Master	22	14.0
	Doctoral	1	0.6
Length of working life	Less than 5 years	11	7.0
	6 to 10 years	28	17.8
	11 to 15 years	30	19.1
	16 to 20 years	31	19.7
	21 to 25 years	43	27.4
	More than 26 years	14	8.9

3.2. Test for Validity and Reliability

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied for the validity of both scales in order to confirm the one-dimensional structure. Strong model fit indexes were obtained in the CFA applied to the IM-11 scale ($\chi^2= 83.7$; $df= 44$; $CFI= .957$; $GFI= .904$; $AGFI= .856$; $RMESA= .076$). Similarly, good levels of model fit indexes were obtained as a result of the CFA applied to the job performance scale ($\chi^2= 19.1$; $df= 9$; $CFI= .988$; $GFI= .961$; $AGFI= .910$; $RMESA= .085$). Model fit values of both scales met the criteria suggested in the literature (Browne and Cudeck, 1993; Byrne, 2001).

On the other hand, the reliability analysis indicated that both scales had high-reliability scores ($\alpha= .922$ for the IM-11 scale; $\alpha= .942$ for the Job Performance scale).

3.3. Correlation Analysis

According to the correlation analysis, job performance has a significant and positive relationship with age ($r = 0.178$; $p < 0.05$) and working year ($r = 0.221$; $p < 0.01$). In other words, as the age and working year increase, the job performance of teachers increases. This means that teachers have experienced over the years. There is a significant and positive relationship between internal marketing and job performance, which are the main variables of the research ($r = 0.196$; $p < 0.05$), (Table 2).

Table 2: Results of correlation analysis

Variables	1	2	3
1. Age	1		
2. Length of working life	,812**	1	
3. Internal marketing	,178*	,181*	1
4. Job performance	190*	,221**	,196*

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

3.4. Hierarchical Regression Analysis

According to hierarchical regression analysis, internal marketing has a significant and positive effect on job performance ($\beta = 0.161$; $p < 0.05$). When the demographic variables

found to be related in the correlation analysis enter the regression analysis, it is seen that their effects on job performance disappear (Table 3).

Table 3: Results of the hierarchical regression analysis

Independent Variables	Job Performance	
	Step 1	Step 2
1. Age	,029	,014
2. Length of working life	,198	,181
3. Internal marketing	-	,161*
<i>F</i>	3.992	4.084
<i>R</i> ²	.049	.074
<i>Adjusted R</i> ²	.037	.056

Note: Standardized beta values were used, **p* <0.05.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The findings obtained in this study show that internal marketing significantly and positively affects the job performance of physical education and sports teachers. There are many studies in the literature that deals with the relationship between internal marketing and other variables in various sectors. These researches include examining the relationship between internal marketing and job performance. For example, in his research on health institutions, Ergün (2013) found that internal marketing positively affected hospital performance. Esitti and Buluk (2018), in their research, found that internal marketing practices had a positive effect on employees' job performance in hospitality businesses. The results of this research support the findings of our study. In educational organizations, the researches on internal marketing on teachers are very low. For example, Dokuzoglu and Eren (2020) examined the effect of internal marketing on the organizational commitment of physical education and sports teachers, and ultimately found that internal marketing positively affected teachers' organizational commitment. Eren and Dokuzoglu (2020) also examined the effect of internal marketing on physical education and sports teachers' turnover intention, and ultimately found that internal marketing had a negative effect on teachers' turnover intentions. In other words, the teachers who are satisfied with the internal marketing practices of the organization do not have turnover intentions. On the other hand, in the sample of physical education and sports teachers, there is no research examining the effect of internal marketing on job performance. Therefore, it can be said that with the results revealed by this study, it resolves a deficiency in the literature.

As a result, this study shows that internal marketing increases the job performance of physical education and sports teachers. There is much evidence in the literature that internal marketing practices increase the motivation of the employees and ensure the success of the organization (Yildiz, 2016). Therefore, it may be suggested that managers of educational organizations should activate their internal marketing practices in order to increase the performance of physical education and sports teachers. In particular, the organizational citizenship behavior of teachers can be achieved by improving the quality

of the relationship in the context of leadership-member interaction (Yildiz, 2011b). Extra-role behavior is known to result in job satisfaction and high performance (Somech and Drach-Zahavy, 2000). In this way, physical education and sports teachers will provide better quality service, and thus the image of the school will increase in the eyes of the students, parents, and society.

About the Author

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